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THE CONCEPT OF SELF-EFFICACY IN PSYCHOLOGY ПОНЯТТЯ САМОЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ У ПСИХОЛОГІЇ

У тезах проаналізовано концепцію самоефективності А. Бандури. Охарактеризовано три властивості самоефективності, що визначають її вплив на поведінку: 1. рівень, що описує уявлення людини про свою спроможність справлятися з однією і тією самою діяльністю за різних ступенів її складності. 2. сила, яка характеризує ступінь впевненості людини в тому, що вона може впоратися з тією чи іншою діяльністю, виконати завдання, що стоять перед нею. 3. узагальненість (широта), яка показує, як переносяться переконання у власній ефективності, сформовані в одній сфері діяльності, на інші.

Ключові слова: *самоефективність, теорія соціального навчання, особистість.*

The first approaches to the study of self-efficacy were identified in foreign psychology in the 50s-60s of the XX century, although the term «self-efficacy» itself appeared later. R. Waid and R. de Charmes were the first researchers to include the phenomenon of self-efficacy in a broader context of motivational factors of behavior (Хекхаузен, 2004). They argue that the more pronounced a person's sense of efficacy and experiences of «identity» are in their consciousness, the more intrinsically motivated they are, with extrinsic motivation unable to compete with intrinsic motivation.

Albert Bandura developed the social-cognitive theory, which emphasizes personal and cognitive factors in human development. According to this theory, behavioral response is not an automatic response to external stimuli; responses to stimuli are activated by the individual.

Bandura introduced the concept of an intermediate variable into the traditional behavioral stimulus-response scheme, and this mechanism became the cognitive processes of personality (Шульц, 2002).

In the late 1970s, the concept of self-efficacy was proposed by Albert Bandura within the framework of social cognitive theory. In 1977, in the article «Self-efficacy: Toward a General Theory of Behavior Change,» Bandura first introduced the concept of self-efficacy, which was defined as follows: «The expectation of efficacy is the belief that an individual is capable of successfully performing the behavior necessary to achieve expected outcomes» (Bandura, 1997).

The concepts of «expectation of effectiveness» and «expectation of results» were separated, because, according to A. Bandura (Bandura, 1997), a

person may know that some actions are followed by a certain result, but not believe in his/her ability to perform these actions.

The central point of the concept of self-efficacy is the idea that belief in one's ability to cope with a certain type of activity is a necessary motivational condition. Bandura believes that the attractiveness of the outcome and the expectation of success are not sufficient to trigger a subject's motivation.

The key determinant is self-efficacy, defined as people's judgment of their abilities to organize and execute the chains of actions required to achieve predetermined predetermined types of performance outcomes (Bandura, 1997).

In his theory A. Bandura identified three properties of self-efficacy that determine its influence on behavior (Bandura, 1986):

1. Level. Describes a person's perceptions of his or her ability to cope with the same activity at different degrees of difficulty. For example, a student can solve a single equation but cannot handle a system of two equations.

2. Strength. Characterizes the degree of a person's confidence that he or she can cope with this or that activity, fulfill the tasks facing him or her. Strength is also manifested in the stability of one's confidence in one's own effectiveness, despite negative past experiences. According to Bandura, weak efficacy expectations will disappear in case of failure, whereas strong self-efficacy stimulates the continuation of activity despite the difficulties encountered (Gordeeva, 2002).

3- Generalizability (breadth). Indicates how beliefs in self-efficacy formed in one area of activity are transferred to others. Albert Bandura distinguishes three levels of generality: narrow (characterizes self-efficacy in a specific task and in specific conditions), medium (in a set of tasks from one sphere of activity), and global (characterizes beliefs in personal efficacy regardless of the field of activity and situation). Accordingly, self-efficacy can differ in different types of activity, so the measurement of generalized personal effectiveness does not predict the level of achievement in specific types of activity.

Studies conducted by A. Bandura and his colleagues have identified six main characteristics of self-efficacy as a personal construct (Бандура, 2000):

- self-efficacy is an assessment of one's own ability to cope with certain tasks, not a personality trait;

- self-efficacy is a private, specific, not global characteristic of an individual; it is not related to an assessment of one's own personality, such as self-esteem, but reflects an individual's confidence in coping with specific tasks;

- self-efficacy depends on the context of activity, so many factors can influence the subject's activity and, consequently, his/her sense of self-efficacy;

- self-efficacy is measured using mastery and competence criteria rather than normative or other comparative characteristics;

- self-efficacy is an expectation of personal mastery of future tasks, so self-efficacy is measured before a person begins to perform an activity;

- self-efficacy is understood as a judgment of the actions a person can perform, regardless of the meaning he or she attaches to them.

Self-efficacy is shaped throughout life by a variety of factors. Bandura identified four main sources of information about self-efficacy (Гордеева, 2002).

The problem of general and private self-efficacy is considered to be one of the most difficult problems to study (Каппара, Сервон, 2003). On the one hand, it is the specificity of self-efficacy that makes it possible to predict success in a particular activity. On the other hand, the concept of self-efficacy is criticized because of the insufficient possibility of generalizing experimental data obtained on the material of any activity. In this regard, Bandura writes that «the optimal level of generality at which self-efficacy is defined varies according to what needs to be predicted and the degree of anticipation demanded by the situation» (Bandura, 1997).